

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH THROUGH GAMES

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Abstract: *The perpetual quest for innovative and effective methods of teaching English has led educators to explore the concept of gamification in language instruction. The notion of incorporating games into the teaching of English has gained significant traction in recent years, and for good reason. Games have the potential to transform the traditional classroom setting into a realm of engagement, excitement, and experiential learning, thereby fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of the English language. This article will delve into the various methods of teaching English through games, highlighting the benefits and advantages of this approach.*

Keywords: *learning environment, fun games, role, benefits, visual materials, cognitive skills, critical thinking*

Introduction: Games absolutely are a fantastic enjoyable when played, however nonetheless there ought to be cautions due to the fact regularly they might also have detrimental effects, for instance, if college students acquired carried away with all the pleasure of the winner, may say or do something that may additionally harm the feeling of any other one. In the second video games are employed in the lessons, the trainer needs to undergo in thought the manager of it in the ideal way so no longer to lose route of it. The instructor has to guarantee that all the contributors revel in the recreation and have a fine experience, in view that the lecture room must now not come to be a region the place college students sense stocked in. Another necessary aspect to hold in thinking is that now not all the video games are appropriate for the school room environment, or the students' a while and levels. It can be difficult to figure out which the proper recreation is and that is a duty of the teacher. It is encouraged for the instructor to pay interest to the most essential standards of a game; that is a sport that balanced fun, project and learning. The

trainer ought to be conscious of the crew of individuals and then figure out the appropriate sport with the dreams the team have to be aiming. The instructor ought to be mindful now not to pick a complex sport that requires a lot of work given that this can also end result in the loss of interest and activity amongst students, and as such it will analyze them nothing. The guidelines of the video games must be made clear on the grounds that the opening of the game, so now not to purpose interruption throughout it and the position of the trainer in this case is to examine and assist the place necessary, and encouraging participants. With the give up of the game, it is advised to do some deliberate endeavor associated to the subject matter of the lesson as it offers college students some time to replicate upon the recreation and the competencies and understanding bought from it. It is viewed vital for instructors to apprehend that amplifying a sport is permissible and ensure instances it may additionally be necessary. Such as, tough video games can be simplified in order to emerge as a project no longer solely for gifted college students but, for much less professional ones, as well. They ought to suit the students' desires and their stage of knowledge.

When to Use Games

The ones who use video games as a mastering device have to additionally take into consideration the time when to use them. According to Hadfield "games ought to be considered a critical section of the language syllabus, now not a fun endeavor for Friday afternoon of for the give up of the term". Games have to be used as section of the lesson plans in order to higher transmit the new competencies to the college students and make them energetic participants. For instance, in video games 'Pictionary' and 'Where shall I go' college students are in a position to higher research vocabulary and exercise the talent of speak me as they are learning. When instructors have to give an explanation for challenging section of grammar, they can use sport taking part in rather of regular teaching. Teachers may also assist inexperienced persons know specific types of grammar with the aid of attractive them in unique video games that fulfill the standards of a traditional instructing that consists of memorizing rules, repetitive drills and so on. In addition, what is indispensable is that college students can advantage from video games their use in actual existence communication. Most of the teachers, attempting to entire their ESL classes

frequently discover video games as a superb answer now not solely to fill their lesson plan, however additionally to hold college students inspired and conscious all through the class. The utilization of video games is justified with the benefits and advantages it brings to the students. They are a gorgeous way to be used in challenging and now not fantastic matters so as video games can make college students greater lively and inclined to analyze even the problematic topics. Games are in the main regarded as warming-up things to do to appeal to the student's attention, in particular throughout free time at the cease of a lecture. Games are important due to the fact they motivate and promote a handy learning. As Lee says: "A recreation ought to no longer be regarded as insignificant or as an exercise to fill in the free time when each the instructor and the college students have nothing to do". Games must current a core thing of instructing a difficulty in an overseas language.

General Benefits of Games

Games do provide a number of advantages for the students. Below are cited some of them in accordance to Casey Malarcher and Martha Lengeling:

"Affective:

- lowers affective filter
- encourages innovative and spontaneous use of language
- promotes communicative competence
- motivates
- enjoyable

Cognitive:

- reinforces
- opinions and extends
- focuses on grammar communicatively

Class Dynamics:

- scholar situated
- trainer acts solely as facilitator
- builds category concord
- fosters complete category participation
- promotes healthful opposition

There are some games that can enhance children's skills:

1. Name games

Name video games are a definitely desirable way to begin a lesson, they are particularly beneficial at the begin of the yr to assist you take note the names of all your new students! Go spherical the circle and have the youth say their title and one of their favorite things. When the subsequent infant introduces themselves, they need to first introduce the baby that went earlier than them and so on till the ultimate infant remembers the names and preferred matters of anyone in the group! This can be made tougher for older students, by means of having a rule that their favorite issue has to start with the equal letter as their first name, or less difficult for youthful students, with the aid of simply having them bear in mind the names.

2. Charades

This is a sport that I've located to be famous with teenagers of all ages! I've used an envelope full of reduce out words, or a set of photograph flashcards for youthful students, to play this. Secretly exhibit a scholar a phrase or flashcard and then have them silently act it out, at the front of the class, whilst the different youngsters name out – in English – what they suppose the secret phrase is. The young people get notable aggressive over this, and the mimes can be hilarious! Charades can additionally be tailored to examine nearly any vocabulary – animals, sports, hobbies, thoughts – so it is without end useful!

3. Pictionary

Similar to charades, however the youth draw the secret phrase rather of performing it out. I've discovered that youngsters love being given to threat to use a marker and whiteboard – and to exhibit off their inventive skills.

4. Stand up if you...

This recreation works exceptional with a large team and you want to have an open house to play in (it would work properly outdoors, if you have an out of doors space!). Get all the teens to structure a massive circle with you standing in the middle. You have to then name out a training such as 'stand up if you're sporting shorts', and every person carrying shorts ought to swap locations with every different in the circle whilst you attempt and steal one of their spots. The infant left in the center then receives to name out the subsequent instruction. This sport can be effortlessly tailored to swimsuit the vocabulary the classification is gaining knowledge of such as appearance, clothing, likes/dislikes, household members, vacations – it's amazing!

One of the most significant advantages of using games in English language instruction is the creation of a low-anxiety atmosphere. Traditional classroom settings often emphasize rote memorization and strict grammar rules, leading to feelings of apprehension and anxiety among students. Games, on the other hand, provide a relaxed and interactive environment where students can freely experiment with language without fear of correction or ridicule. This relaxed atmosphere enables students to take risks, ask questions, and engage in meaningful interactions, all of which are essential for language acquisition.

Another benefit of teaching English through games is the promotion of authentic language use. Games often simulate real-life scenarios, requiring students to use language in a practical and meaningful way. For instance, role-playing games can be designed to mimic everyday situations, such as ordering food at a restaurant or participating in a job interview. This approach encourages students to employ language in a functional and communicative manner, rather than simply memorizing grammatical rules or vocabulary lists. By engaging in authentic language use, students develop a deeper understanding of language structures, vocabulary, and cultural nuances.

In addition to promoting authentic language use, games can also be tailored to address specific linguistic skills, such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing. For example, listening comprehension games can be designed to improve students' ability to understand spoken English, while speaking games can focus on enhancing students' fluency and pronunciation. Reading games, such as quizzes or crosswords, can be used to develop students' vocabulary and comprehension skills, while writing games can help students practice grammar and sentence structure. By targeting specific skills, games can help teachers pinpoint areas where students require additional support or practice.

Furthermore, games can be adapted to cater to diverse learning styles and abilities. For instance, visual learners can benefit from games that incorporate images, diagrams, or videos, while auditory learners can engage with games that rely on music, podcasts, or audio recordings. Moreover, games can be designed to accommodate students with special needs, such as cognitive or physical disabilities. By incorporating multiple modalities and adapting games to meet individual needs, teachers can create an inclusive and supportive learning environment.

Another significant advantage of teaching English through games is the promotion of collaborative learning. Many language games require students to work in pairs or small groups, fostering a sense of teamwork, cooperation, and mutual support. This approach not only encourages social interaction and bonding but also helps to build confidence and reduce shyness among students. By working together to solve language-based challenges, students develop essential skills such as problem-solving, critical thinking, and effective communication.

In addition to promoting collaborative learning, games can also be used to facilitate cultural exchange and understanding. Many language games can be designed to simulate cultural scenarios or traditions, providing students with a unique opportunity to learn about different customs, values, and ways of life. For instance, games can be created to teach students about holidays, festivals, or celebrations from around the world, promoting cultural sensitivity, appreciation, and understanding.

Finally, the incorporation of games into English language instruction can lead to increased student motivation and engagement. Games have the power to captivate and entertain, often rendering language learning an enjoyable and rewarding experience. By incorporating elements of fun and competition, games can motivate students to practice language skills regularly, even outside the classroom. Moreover, the sense of accomplishment and achievement that comes with winning or completing a game can boost students' confidence and self-esteem, leading to a more positive attitude towards language learning.

Conclusion.

In conclusion, the incorporation of games into English language instruction offers a multitude of benefits and advantages. By creating a low-anxiety atmosphere, promoting authentic language use, targeting specific linguistic skills, catering to diverse learning styles, promoting collaborative learning, facilitating cultural exchange, and increasing student motivation, games can revolutionize the way we teach and learn English. As educators, it is our responsibility to harness the power of games and gamification to create a more engaging, effective, and enjoyable language learning experience for our students. By doing so, we can unlock the full potential of our students, empowering them to become confident, competent, and enthusiastic users of the English language.

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